

Research Article

The Future of Media in Thailand: Influencing Factors and Satisfaction Using Streaming Media Service With The Membership Fee

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Abstract: Thai television media industry has changed from Linear TV to Video-on-demand because it easy and flexible to watch. Video-on-demand services are available in both paid and free formats which the membership paid service has grow tremendously in Thailand. Nevertheless, the increasing number of competitors in the market makes it difficult for viewers to pay for all platforms. It is impossible to predict the future of Thailand's media market. The researcher chose to study in the streaming service with a membership fee, which is currently favored to analyze this industry's future. This research aims to study the factors influencing the decision to purchase online media services by studying the effects between relaxation, ad-free, individual viewing, exclusivity feeling, anti-piracy, and technology-engaged factors to the satisfaction of using service, including satisfaction with the decision to purchase streaming media services. Also, study the buffering issues affecting the relationship between satisfaction and purchase decision. The researcher used 385 sets of questionnaires to collect data from Thai online media members. The result shows that relaxation, technology engaged, exclusivity feeling, and anti-piracy factors affect the service's satisfaction, and satisfaction is part of the service purchase decision. However, the buffering problem has reduced the purchasing decision.

Keywords: Future, Streaming media, Purchase decision, Influencing factors, Satisfaction.

Introduction

The original media industry has changed from analog to digital system. The coming ages of streaming media, especially in the form of monthly payments or SVOD, have influenced the linear industry not to grow as expected. The first problem is that the original TV has lost revenue from advertising sales decreased due to people are turning to invest in digital online markets and because users think streaming service can meet their needs more precisely. Moreover, the growth rate of

SVOD is so fast that it makes many believe the traditional TV industry will die, but as more and more competitors in the online streaming market cause, the second problems followed. The second problem is too many choices. The excessive video may make people discover the things that appealed to users may not meet all of the essential requirements at all and may cause consumers to hesitate. Some people feel a sense of monotony because if they want to see each service provider's original content, consumers will have to pay a viewing fee for all service providers, whose usage is not worth the cost. Due to the viewers themselves will not be able to watch all TV programs on every platform.

The problems mentioned above lead to the question about the future of the media industry. People will unsubscribe from the streaming platform due to increased competition and return to traditional TV. Alternatively, there will be a new way that will allow viewers to make decisions more comfortable in the future. Viewers' needs, and satisfaction seem to determine what the media industry in Thailand will look like. The researcher will start to study further from the current situation, which is believed that the paid membership streaming media format is a model that can meet users' needs as much as possible because it is accessible and has a high market growth rate. Furthermore, the researcher will use the factors that viewers say are the difference between linear TV and streaming TV. Also, factors that providers cannot control, external factors, to analyze these factors affect satisfaction with the purchase of streaming media services or not.

Literature Review

Differences between traditional and new media

Traditional media refers to media that originated at an early age. For example, newspapers, radio, and television, these media are mass media that reach the mass audience. It is one-way communication; the receiver receives only one way. Those who send messages cannot know the effects that occur at that time; consumers of the media cannot respond or comment on the media. The original media will be called Linear TV or Terrestrial television, a TV that has scheduled programming and is a free TV that supports operational advertisements.

New media is a new type of communication that is happening today. Technology has come to engage in communication. It makes communication more modern. The new media also causes people to receive messages regardless of who is in every corner of the world, and they can respond or comment on the media. People can receive news quickly, and clearly, distributing the news is

simple. New television formats may be called Over-the-top (OTT), video on demand (VOD), or streaming TV.

The advantages and disadvantages of tradition and new media.

The researcher took the results from the survey of the Kantar Media (2016) research to study the difference between new media and traditional media in viewer's or users' opinions. The results from the survey of real users said that watching linear TV programs has outstanding advantages in terms of equality. Viewers can simultaneously watch the program, causing no incidents of content spoilers and subsequently creating dissatisfaction, which is more suitable for news or sports programs. In contrast, most Americans say that Linear TV is not free to use because all TV programs are scheduled to be broadcast. The ads that make audiences wait are significant disadvantages.

On the other hand, video on demand can be divided into two formats, free and paid video on demand. The use of free VOD, mostly in the audience's case, missed the program that was broadcast on traditional TV and wants to follow it. If not, it is likely to use the service because there is a program that users have a plan to watch.

The pros and cons of the paid streaming format in the viewers' opinion found that the advantage is diversity; users have much high-quality content to watch from many countries. Moreover, they said that the paid streaming system is challenging for viewers to find content if users do not have a favorite program. Due to overwhelming content, young and technology-savvy will receive recommendations via social media where friends who are also members of service comments or posted about the program they like. In contrast to older and less tech-savvy people, they have less trust in recommendations from other people's views. The distinct disadvantage of this type is the service's cost, which may not be covered in all cases, the disappearance of some content due to contract expiration, and buffering issues, which is the same as free video-on-demand.

In this research, the researcher focused on the video-on-demand media in the SVOD format because it is a media format that has experienced high growth during the past 13 years and still has a continuous growth rate at present. It can be deduced that this type of media is favorable, or this media service meets most users' needs.

Concepts and theories about consumer behavior.

Consumer behavior theory is a study of individuals, groups, or organizations choosing, purchasing, using products or services, thought, or experience that meets consumer needs (Kotler

and Keller, 2014: 187). Serirat (2003) examines the motivation that leads to the purchase of products by describing consumers' behavior, which is the response or decision that arises from the act of stimuli on the feeling of the buyer.

The consumer behavior model is the study of incentives that lead to product purchasing decisions, beginning with creating stimuli that stimulate demand through buyers' sentiments, which compares the black box. The manufacturer or seller cannot make predictions in which the buyer's characteristics influence the buyer's thoughts, and there will be a buyer's response or the buyer's purchase decision.

Figure 1: The S-R Theory Model (Chen et al., 2016: 110)

Kotler (2014) describes the consumer's behavior by using the S-R Theory in the form of consumer behavior's model. The model's starting point is that a stimulus first enters a desire and then a response. The stimulation may occur both inside the body or internal stimulus and outside the body or external stimulus. Marketers must pay attention and organize both internal and external stimuli so that consumers want products or services. The stimulus can be considered as an incentive to buy products or buying motives.

In this research, the researcher is interested in studying only the factors of external stimulation. People do not pay much attention to external factors in their research because it is considered an uncontrollable factor. However, this external factor has a massive impact on the business. This section is part of other stimuli in the model of the S-R theory. Marketers cannot control this type of stimulation because they are outside the organization. Eiamsri (2011) discussed PESTLE analysis to analyze the macro-environment, especially the external environment that consists of political, economic, sociocultural, technological, legal, and environmental factors. The researcher studies and selects the advantages that the audience likes from the new media to match with external factors making it able to be organized into five categories.

Social factors, exclusivity feeling, is like a community. People will feel special can be an incentive for people interested in attending (Talbert, 2016). PwC (2019) shows that 36% of 1,000

people in the United States agree to subscribe to streaming media members just to watch the exclusive videos on each service provider.

Personal factors, each person has different characteristics, which are called personality. These characteristics arise from adaptation to society or governance. (Kotler & Armstrong 2009, p. 172.) Nielsen (2017) found that homes with many children watching linear TV co-watching have a higher rate than watching OTT co-watching. IAB Digital Video Center of Excellence (2017) 93% of people said TV big screen is an essential tool for co-viewing, and the linear TV is the highest participation rate among viewers. However, in contrast, the OTT service co-viewing is more interactive and enjoyable than linear TV. Tech-savvy or technology engaged means people who understand the technology and keep up with the trend of IT. According to Kantar media (2016), the older participants were generally less tech-engaged and less likely to explore all the features offered. There is no tech-savvy person who does not use VOD as an option. The current SVOD format will not be broadcast interstitial advertisements, which features is called ad-free. (NBTC, 2017) Westcott, Loucks, Ciampa & Srivastava (2019) say that the ad's total duration for 8 minutes, or 13% per hour, is still the amount that viewers think is fair and acceptable.

Psychological factors, motivation is a desire that drives people to find satisfaction. Relaxation is considered part of the second hierarchy in Maslow's hierarchy of needs. (Kotler & Armstrong 2009). Watching videos or TV is also an activity to relieve stress as Wheeler (2015) found that people with anxiety tend to watch television programs for relaxation.

Political and law factors, Thai people are accustomed to consuming illegal movies because control is still considered difficult (Inpo, 2016). However, Phuthorn (2017) say that some people in Thailand are ready to support licensed products and services if they can import even more things into the country.

Technological factors, there may be a high-speed internet jamming, resulting in data that is known as buffering issues. This problem causes sudden service pause to download (Lyakhov & Sidorkin, 2008), which is less happen on the Linear TV system. Chang (2016), 66% of the 1,000 respondents said they were disappointed when the video stopped to wait for the buffer, and nearly 40% decided not to come back to watch a video stream that has failed to download. Clearly that users cannot endure waiting for this buffering. Nevertheless, it is still unclear whether it may lead to termination membership.

The black box is a buyer's conscience that manufacturers or sellers cannot know, so they have to try to find the buyer's conscience. The buyer's conscience is influenced by the buyer's nature and the decision-making process of the buyer.

The buyer's response is the result of the influence of factors and the mechanism of the buying decision process in the black box. If the response is positive, marketers will notice that consumers choose the product to buy, choose the product's brand to buy, choose the store to buy, choose the time of purchase, and choose the amount to be purchased. If the response is negative, consumers will not buy products or services.

Methodology

The research is quantitative. It is in the form of survey research by using questionnaires to be a tool for data collection to study the behavior and factors that lead to the purchase decision on streaming service. The researcher used the judgmental or purposive sampling method that the questionnaires distributed to Thai respondents who are currently subscribed to or who have subscribed to streaming media services to get sample information from media channels that have the highest market growth rate at present. The researcher also used nonprobability sampling to collect data by distributing questionnaires online on March 20 - April 10, 2020.

The researcher takes the numbers of a sample size from the assumptions of the National Broadcasting and Telecommunication Commission (2017) that Thailand would have several 1,176,134 respondents streaming media services in 2019, resulting in this study to use this hypothesis and use the calculation formula from SurveyMonkey that was developed from Taro Yamane in the determination of sample size. The researcher specified the confidence level is 95%; the acceptable tolerance level is 5%, or at the statistical significance level 0.05. The result found that the appropriate sample group for this study will be 385 people.

The research variables consist of relaxation, ads-free, individual-viewing, exclusivity, anti-piracy, and technology engaged as independent variables. Satisfaction is both a dependent variable and an independent variable. In the case of finding a relationship with all 6 previous variables, satisfaction will be the dependent variable. However, in the case of finding a relationship with purchase decision on streaming service, satisfaction will be in the form of an independent variable, with buffering issues acting as a moderator variable in this relationship.

Figure 2: Conceptual Framework

The questionnaire was divided into four sections. The first section, information about online viewing behavior, is a preliminary screening question in the form of a checklist by selecting one answer. The next section is information about evaluating opinions about relaxation, ads-free, individual viewing, exclusivity, anti-piracy, and technology-engaged factors when choosing to use streaming media service. Section 3 is information about the satisfaction and purchasing decision on streaming services. Section 2 and 3 are in the form of the Five-Point Likert Scales method. The last section is the demographic information of the respondents, answering by select only one answer.

The researcher will analyze information about viewing behavior and respondents' general profile by using frequency, mean, percentage, and standard deviation for the hypothesis analysis of the research related to 6 groups of factors: relaxation, ads-free, individual-viewing, exclusivity feeling, anti-piracy, and technology-engaged. Moreover, additional factors like buffering issues factor, which the researcher will use various statistical methods as follows.

1. Multiple linear regression analysis to study the relationship between 6 groups of independent variables with the following variable is satisfaction using streaming media. The researcher will specify the statistical significance level at 95%.

2. Hierarchical multiple regression analysis to study multiple regression equations for the study of satisfaction affects the purchase decision of watching streaming services, which has the buffering issue factor as a moderator variable and determines 0.05.

Conclusion

The results showed that the sample consisted of 385 people, most of whom were 355 female and male 30. Most respondents were 21-35 years, followed by less than or equal to 20 years. The sample group aged 51-60 years old is the age with the least questionnaire responses. The respondents were single 86.75%, followed by marital for 12.73%, and the divorce 0.52%. The sample group consisted of 43.38% students or 43.38% followed by the occupation of private company 29.35%, and servants/state enterprise employees, representing 10.91%,

Most of the respondents watched the program via smartphone for 90.39%, followed by computers/laptops and smart TVs for 56.62% and 44.94%. The last is the tablet 38.96%. Most of which are watched daily 45.97%, and each time they watch for 3-4 hours, representing 42.08%. The most streaming platform that respondents use the most is Netflix 90.91%, followed by VIU, WeTV, and Youtube premiums for 47.79%, 34.29, and 24.42%. Top 3 types of programs that respondents liked the most are dramas or long series representing 89.90%, followed by gameshow, variety, survivor programs 19.16%, and movies 4.88%.

The researcher found that most of them need entertainment/relaxation/stress relief to use streaming media services followed by news and stories to chat with others, accounting for 35.28% and 25.55%, respectively, and decided to buy online streaming media services by themselves 78.90%. The person influenced the respondents of watching the program, followed by friends representing 12.40% and family with 5%

The factors influencing the satisfaction of using online media to watch programs.

Table 1: Variables obtained from the regression model (Model Summary) of the factors influencing the satisfaction with the use of online streaming media services

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	0.487	0.237	0.225	0.549

From table 1, it can be explained about the factors that influence the satisfaction of using streaming platform 23.7%. In contrast, the remaining 76.3% is due to the influence of other factors.

Table 2: Multiple regression analysis of factors affecting the satisfaction of using streaming services (Coefficients)

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
(Constant)	1.735	0.275		6.309	0.000*
Relaxation factors	0.276	0.051	0.274	5.448	0.000*
Ad-free factors	-0.011	0.042	-0.012	-0.268	0.789
Individual-viewing factors	0.064	0.045	0.070	1.415	0.158
Exclusivity feeling factors	0.076	0.027	0.132	2.771	0.006*
Anti-piracy factors	0.082	0.036	0.110	2.321	0.021*
Technology engaged factors	0.156	0.042	0.180	3.691	0.000*

*With statistical significance at the level of 0.05

Table 2 shows that when considering the value of sig, researchers can conclude that four factors significantly affect the satisfaction with the use of online streaming media services at the statistical level 0.05. The beta coefficient, which represents the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable, is that the independent variables with high beta values mean that significantly affect dependent variables. It can be sorted in descending order, relaxation, technology-engaged, exclusivity feeling, and anti-piracy factors. The results of the regression analysis can answer each hypothesis of the research as follows.

The t-test statistic of relaxation, technology engaged, exclusivity feeling, and anti-piracy factors have significant value at 0.000, 0.000, 0.006, and 0.021, respectively, which are less than 0.05. Therefore, accept the hypothesis and interpret that the factors of relaxation technology engaged, exclusivity feeling, and anti-piracy has a positive effect on satisfaction with statistical significance at the level of 0.05. However, the t-test statistic of ad-free and individual-viewing factors have significant value at 0.789 and 0.158, which are higher than 0.05. Thus, reject the hypothesis and interpret it as ad-free, and individual viewing factors have not a positive effect on satisfaction with statistical significance at the level of 0.05.

The satisfaction affects the purchase decision on online streaming media services, which have the factor of buffering issue as a moderator variable.

Table 3: Variables obtained from regression analysis (Model Summary) of satisfaction influence the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming media services, which have the factor of buffering issue as a moderator variable.

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	0.556	0.309	0.305	0.498	0.309	65.415	2	292	0.000
2	0.574	0.329	0.322	0.492	0.020	8.515	1	291	0.004

However, there are still buffering issues that affect the relationship between satisfaction and service purchase decisions. The researcher used multiple regression analysis methods to find the relationship between satisfaction and influence on purchase decision on online streaming media service, which has the factor of buffering issue as a moderator variable. From table 3, model 1 R Square equals 0.309, which means that the satisfaction and buffering issue factor can explain the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming media services 30.9%.

The model 2, the coefficient of prediction (R Square) equals 0.309, means that the satisfaction, the buffering issue factor, the interaction between service satisfaction and buffering issue factors as a moderator variable able to explain the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming media services 32.9%, increasing 2.0% (R Square Change = 0.020)

Table 4: The results of the ANOVA analysis of satisfaction influence the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming media services, which have buffering issue factor as a moderator variable.

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	32.500	2	16.250	65.415	0.000
	Residual	72.537	292	0.248		
	Total	105.037	294			
2	Regression	34.562	3	11.521	47.571	0.000
	Residual	70.475	291	0.242		
	Total	105.037	294			

To prove whether the factors discussed affect the decision to purchase a streaming media service. Therefore, ANOVA was analyzed by statistical principles, with the hypotheses being used for analysis as follows.

H0: All factors do not affect the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming services.

H1: At least 1 factor affects the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming services.

From determining the significance level at 0.05, the test results in table 4, step 1 and step 2 obtained the significance value equal to 0.000, which is less than the significance level. Therefore, accept H1. At least 1 factor that affects the purchase decision of watching programs on an online streaming service.

Table 5: Analysis of hierarchical multiple regression of satisfaction influences the purchase decision on online streaming service which has the factor of buffering issue as a moderator variable.

Variable	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
Step 1					
(Constant)	2.437	0.219		11.148	0.000*
Satisfaction	0.532	0.047	0.559	11.432	0.000*
Buffering issue factors	-0.050	0.033	-0.073	-1.496	0.136
Step 2					
(Constant)	4.435	0.718		6.178	0.000*
Satisfaction	0.052	0.171	0.054	0.304	0.761
Buffering issue factors	-0.610	0.195	-0.895	-3.132	0.002*
Satisfaction × Buffering issue factors	0.134	0.046	1.015	2.918	0.004*

*With statistical significance at the level of 0.05

From table 5, it is found that when considering the value of Sig., It can be concluded that step 1 has only satisfaction in use influencing the purchase decision on online streaming service at the statistical level 0.05. The second step, buffering issue and the interaction between the satisfaction

in use and the moderator variable influences the purchase decision on online streaming service at the statistical level 0.05. The result of the regression analysis able to answer each hypothesis of the research as follows

The research in Table 5, it can be seen that satisfaction has a t-test with a Sig. value of 0.000 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, accept assumption and interpret that satisfaction positively affects the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming service with statistical significance at the level of 0.05

Moreover, the interaction between satisfaction and buffering issue as moderator variable has a t-test with sig. equal to 0.004 which is less than 0.05. Therefore, accept the hypothesis and interpret that the buffering issue makes the relationship between satisfaction and the purchase decision on online streaming service weaker. The buffering issue acts as a moderator variable to control the relationship between satisfaction with the purchase decision of watching programs on online streaming with the statistic level at 0.05.

Discussion

The research result shows that the factors that affect service satisfaction and lead to the decision to buy streaming media services can be grouped into six groups, each of which can be further explained in each list:

1. Relaxing factors. Thai people are facing stress from work, school, or even life issues. Watching videos from streaming media services is a natural, convenient, and inexpensive way to invest in a relaxing activity. Also, able to use the service anytime, anywhere. This factor makes consumers decide to buy online media services.

2. Advertising-free factors. Thai people accustomed to the format of viewing programs through the original media that have already shown advertising. Also, some people think that watching advertisements allows them to keep up with social trends. Consumers, therefore, do not pay much attention to this factor.

3. Individual-viewing factors. Thai consumers believe that watching TV programs with family, friends, or acquaintances is considered an activity to strengthen relationships. Although some people like to make decisions or choose to watch the program themselves, most consumers do not pay much attention to this factor.

4. Exclusivity feeling factors. May be due to the use of streaming platform services often has a special privilege for members. These are things that attract consumers' attention because they can make consumers feel proud and can pick some topics to discuss in society. This factor makes consumers decide to buy online media services.

5. Anti-piracy factors. Due to the low quality of picture and sound in pirated service, together with the support of government and operators, viewers are interested in turning to use legal services because they have better quality. Therefore, this factor makes consumers purchase online media services.

6. Technology engaged factors. Streaming services platform requires knowledge of the technology involved in the use. Moreover, people believe following technology trends can create social interaction. This factor makes consumers decide to buy media services.

The researcher has studied whether the use of streaming media services influences the purchase of the service based on the satisfaction of users. The analysis shows that from a sample of 385 people, everyone is satisfied with using the service and lead to the need to continue using or purchasing streaming services. However, there are still buffering issues that affect the relationship between satisfaction and service purchase decisions.

The researcher studied buffering issues or the loading problem and found that waiting to be loaded causes much annoyance to users. This buffering issue also has a moderate impact on service users to cancel members. The root cause of this problem is insufficient for internet speed. If the internet signal is not fast or not stable enough, the platform will face problems that cause discomfort in watching programs. It can be said that the buffering issue factor makes consumers less likely to purchase streaming media services.

Recommendation

The researcher would like to summarize recommendations for those interested or involved to use it as information. To further improve and develop programs in various sections, which will be explained according to the factors that affect the satisfaction of using online media platforms, from high to low as follows.

1. Relaxation factors. Entrepreneurs should consider the target audience's needs and behavior to adapt to the trend of consumers changing all the time. Moreover, to make the service platform accessible, compete for a market share, and have a higher operating income by presenting new

content that focuses on a long series that may buy the copyright from foreign countries, especially Korea.

2. Technology-engaged factors. Mobile phones are considered devices that have a huge role in daily life because they are easily accessed anytime and anywhere. To expand the user base, entrepreneurs or developers should design a beautiful, modern, easy to use and hassle-free platform for viewing on a computer screen, on the TV screen, on mobile or tablet applications to increase the convenience for consumers.

3. Exclusivity feeling factors. Entrepreneurs should create an identity for their services so that consumers can feel special. There may be importing or creating video content in which only one platform can broadcast. In this way, production houses may influence the steaming media industry because they can be the media producers and broadcast their video content themselves without selling the copyright to service providers from each platform.

4. Anti-piracy factors. The streaming media service in Thailand still has a pirated service. Of course, the quality of sneaking of both pictures and sound clarity is quite low, so the entrepreneurs should raise the advantages of their video content that offers both clarities, images, and sound and reduce the service fees not to be too expensive.

5. Buffering issue factors. Entrepreneurs should be aware that these services require internet access and should provide support, which may be jointly invested with domestic internet providers to strengthen the signal to cover the user's needs. This approach may lead to the collaboration of streaming providers and internet providers, or more internet providers turn into one of the streaming platform providers themselves in the future.

Suggestions for future studies

1. This research is conducted data collection by using online questionnaires only, which may cause missing important information. Therefore, the next research should use a qualitative research model such as in-depth interviews, focus groups, and observations for data collection for more precise and more comprehensive information.

2. Study of attitudes and uses of online streaming services, including a thorough analysis of the program's format and content, whether each side effects the decision to watch the program or not.

3. This research studies only online media programs, so next time research should study the comparison online and offline programs to find differences and evaluate each program's strategy to create a competitive advantage.

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